

Quantization of Klein-Gordon Scalar Field in Cosmological Inertial Frame

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Abstract: In the Cosmological Special Theory of Relativity, we quantized Klein-Gordon scalar field. We treat Lagrangian density and Hamiltonian in quantized Klein-Gordon scalar field in the Cosmological Special Theory of Relativity

Keywords: Cosmological inertial frame; Klein-Gordon scalar field; Hamiltonian; Quantization

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1. INTRODUCTION

Our article's aim is that we make quantization of Klein-Gordon scalar field in Cosmological Special Theory of Relativity (CSTR).

At first, space-time relations are in cosmological special theory of relativity (CSTR).[1]

$$ct = \gamma(ct + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega^2(t_0)x'), \quad x\Omega(t_0) = \gamma(\Omega(t_0)x' + v_0\Omega(t_0)t')$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(t_0)y &= \Omega(t_0)y', \\ \Omega(t_0)z &= \Omega(t_0)z' \end{aligned}, \quad \gamma = 1 / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v_0^2}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0)}, \quad t_0 \text{ is cosmological time} \quad (1)$$

Proper time is

$$\begin{aligned} d\tau^2 &= dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0) [dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2] \\ &= dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0) [dx'^2 + dy'^2 + dz'^2], \quad t_0 \text{ is cosmological time} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Angular frequency-wave number relation is in CSTR.

$$\omega' = \gamma(\omega - v_0\Omega(t_0)k_1), \quad k_1' = \gamma(k_1 - \frac{v_0}{c^2} \Omega(t_0)\omega)$$

$$k_2' = k_2, k_3' = k_3, \gamma = 1 / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v_0^2}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0)} \quad (3)$$

2. QUANTIZATION OF KLEIN-GORDON SCALAR FIELD IN CSTR

Lagrangian density of Klein-Gordon scalar field in CSTR,

$$L = -\frac{1}{2} \left[-\left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t}\right)^2 \Omega(t_0) + \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \vec{\nabla} \phi \cdot \vec{\nabla} \phi + \frac{m_0^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi^2 \right] \quad (4)$$

Hence, Euler-Lagrange equation is in CSTR,

$$\partial_\mu \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial (\partial_\mu \phi)} \right] - \frac{\partial L}{\partial \phi} = \left[\Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\right)^2 - \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \nabla^2 + \frac{m_0^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] \phi = 0 \quad (5)$$

Hamiltonian of Klein-Gordon scalar field is in CSTR,

$$H = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t}\right)^2 \Omega(t_0) + \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \vec{\nabla} \phi \cdot \vec{\nabla} \phi + \frac{m_0^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi^2 \right] \quad (6)$$

The Klein-Gordon scalar field is divided by positive frequency mode and negative frequency mode.

$$\phi(x) = \phi^{(+)}(x) + \phi^{(-)}(x) \quad (7)$$

The positive frequency mode is

$$\phi^{(+)}(x) = \int \frac{d^3 k}{(2\pi)^3 2\omega_k} a(k) f_k(x) \quad (8)$$

The negative frequency mode is

$$\phi^{(-)}(x) = \int \frac{d^3 k}{(2\pi)^3 2\omega_k} a^{(+)}(k) f_k(x) \quad (9)$$

In this time, $f_k(x)$ is

$$f_k(x) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3 2\omega_k} \exp \left[i \left(\frac{\omega_k t}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{x} \sqrt{\Omega(t_0)} \right) \right] \quad (10)$$

In this time,

$$\frac{\omega_k}{c} = \left(k^2 + \frac{m_0^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (11)$$

Quantization of complex scalar field is in CSTR,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(x) = & \int \frac{d^3 k}{(2\pi)^3 2\omega_k} [a(k) \exp \{ i \left(\frac{\omega_k t}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{x} \sqrt{\Omega(t_0)} \right) \}] \\ & + \int \frac{d^3 k}{(2\pi)^3 2\omega_k} [b^+(k) \exp \{ -i \left(\frac{\omega_k t}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{x} \sqrt{\Omega(t_0)} \right) \}] \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\phi^+(x) = \int \frac{d^3 k}{(2\pi)^3 2\omega_k} [b(k) \exp \{ i \left(\frac{\omega_k t}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{x} \sqrt{\Omega(t_0)} \right) \}]$$

$$+ \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^2 2\omega_k} [a^+(k) \exp\{-i(\frac{\omega_k t}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{x} \sqrt{\Omega(t_0)})\}] \quad (13)$$

Hence, Hamiltonian H is in CSTR,

$$H = \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3 2\omega_k} [a^+(k)a(x) + b^+(k)b(k)] \quad (14)$$

In this time,

$$[a(k), a^+(k')] = (2\pi)^3 2\omega_k \delta^3(\vec{k} - \vec{k}')$$

$$[b(k), b^+(k')] = (2\pi)^3 2\omega_k \delta^3(\vec{k} - \vec{k}')$$
(15)

3. CONCLUSION

We quantized Klein-Gordon scalar field in CSTR. We treat Lagrangian density and Hamiltonian.

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